
The Mediating Effect of Coaching and Mentoring Competencies in the Relationship between Instructional Skills and Job Performance of Teachers

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ABSTRACT: This study determined the mediating effect of coaching and mentoring competencies on the relationship between instructional skills and job performance of teachers. The quantitative research design of descriptive-correlational type of study was employed in this study and a sample of 300 teachers was taken randomly from the current teachers in the public junior high schools of Island Garden City of Samal division. Modified questionnaires were used to gather participant data, which underwent content validity and reliability analysis. The data were analyzed using the Mean, Pearson-r, and Multiple Regression Analysis. The results reveal that the levels of coaching and mentoring competencies are high, and the respondents' instructional skills and job performance are very high. Moreover, a significant relationship existed between these variables. A significant relationship between instructional skills and coaching and mentoring competencies was significant. A significant relationship between coaching and mentoring competencies and job performance was statistically significant. A significant relationship between instructional skills and job performance was also significant. The extent of the influence of predictor variables on job performance of teachers was proven in the study. This implies that coaching and mentoring significantly enhance teachers' instructional skills, leading to improved job performance, emphasizing the importance of structured support and collaboration in professional development.

KEYWORDS: education, students, teachers, coaching and mentoring, instructional skills, job performance, mediation, Philippines

1. INTRODUCTION

The standard of the job performance among teachers of the area has been an issue of concern following poor attitudes and apparently perceived lack of commitment to duty by a number of secondary school teachers. That many of the teachers employed in secondary school are truancy as seen in their poor disposition to carrying out instructional responsibilities; how they arrive to work; their regularity in attending classes or school; their record keeping disposition and disciplinary disposition; indicates that they do their job in a rejectable manner (Olaifa, Oyekunle, NijiOlawepo, Adeoye, & Olaifa 2024).

In the Philippines' education system, teachers encounter many problems that must address properly due to job dissatisfaction and poor performance (Tamana & Sanchez, 2024). Not attending to the needs of their dependents negatively affects the welfare and productivity of instructors limiting the amount they produce (Duplon, Ventura, & Decena, 2022). However, lack of job performance indicated that they were students with poor performance in their class work. (Matemba, 2024). Besides, this has a toll on the employee's mental health as well as his or her capacity to perform a certain work or job in most situations (Taguiam, 2021).

The job performance remains central in the creation and accomplishment of functions across all disciplines namely: education, society, local, state, national and global, institutions and community organizational development and planning. Job performance management provides a structure for the employees' systematic improvement and the enhancement of educational institutions as organizations (Kotherja & Hamzallari, 2022). Enthusiastic teachers are more likely to engage students, create a positive classroom environment, and foster a love of learning, all contributing to better student outcomes. This underscores the critical role of teacher job performance in influencing students' success (Aldrup, Klusmann, & Lüdtko, 2022).

2. METHOD

2.1 Research Respondents

The study involved on the junior high school teachers in the Department of Education in the Province of Davao del Norte, Division of Island Garden City of Samal, Philippines. There are 403 junior high school teachers in the division, and 300 junior teachers were selected as respondents to ensure a comprehensive analysis of the subject under investigation. For path analysis, the

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selected number of participants satisfies the conventional condition of 300-499 participants, a reasonable sample size recommended by Tabachnick and Fidell (1996) and Comney and Lee (1992). Thus, this study's 300-sample size would be sufficient for the analysis.

The researcher used a stratified sampling technique to ensure the fair distribution of the respondents in secondary teachers in Babak District, Samal District, and Kaputian District. According to Shi (2015), stratified sampling is a technique that divides the entire population into uniform subpopulations known as strata according to traits. The study's respondents choose wisely to ensure they belong to one stratum. This way, the research goals were thoroughly examined, and the findings were trustworthy and legitimate. This is purposefully included in response to the survey on the mediating role of coaching and mentoring competencies on the relationship between instructional skills and teachers' job performance.

The inclusion criteria included junior high school teachers who are bonified—that is, who are officially hired by the Department of Education, do not violate any laws, and are not subject to any criminal liability—in the Province of Davao del Norte Island Garden City of Samal. The exclusion criterion is considered as the study respondents do not include substitute teachers, not a bonified junior high school teacher, and if the teacher was subjected to criminal liability. In the case of withdrawal from the included respondents, they were forced and given the liberty to withdraw without being penalized as their choices and decisions were respected. The participants will be disqualified from participating in the study if they meet any of the following criteria: they are unwilling to participate in the research and when they resign from the school during the study. Moreover, based on the experiences of the participants when withdrawing from the study, the participant must inform the researcher that they no longer wish to participate in the study, and they have the discretion to inform the researcher of the reasons for withdrawing or not.

2.2 Materials and Instrument

The study employed questionnaires adapted from different studies and modified to the context of respondents. The instrument was divided into instructional skills, job performance, and coaching and mentoring competencies. The first part shall assess the instructional skills; the scale consists of 25 items, which include seven dimensions of lecturing skills: structure, explication, stimulation, validation, instruction, comprehension, and activation. The items were partly adapted from Vorst and van Engelenburg's (1992) Uvalon items and modified by the researcher. It has a Cronbach's reliability of 0.99, meaning it has reliable and internally valid ratings. The second part shall assess the job performance. A questionnaire designed self-rating questionnaire (TJPSQ) was developed to measure the job performance of teachers. This questionnaire is comprised of 25 items, which are divided into four subscales: teaching skills, management skills, discipline and regularity, and interpersonal relations. It achieved a Cronbach's reliability of 0.81, rated good after the pilot testing.

The third and last tool shall assess the mediating effect of coaching and mentoring competencies, adapted from a study entitled "Mentor Competencies Questionnaire" (MCQ) by CMI (2016), which includes committed to own learning, interest in developing others, managing the relationship, managing the goals, self-awareness, behavioral awareness, communicating through concepts and models, communicating through language, business savvy, big picture, me generally. The MCQ model questionnaire consisted of 70 questions. The reliability obtained a Cronbach alpha value of 0.95, which means that the tool is highly acceptable and has a high internal consistency, making it a reliable tool for gathering data. All these instruments use a 5-point Likert type of scale.

The responses on instructional skills, job performance, and coaching and mentoring competencies were analyzed using the scale based on the range of means with its descriptive level and interpretation. The very high descriptive level with a range of mean 4.20-5.00 which means measures of instructional skills, job performance, and coaching and mentoring competencies are always manifested or always evident. High descriptive level with a range of mean 3.40 – 4.29, which means measures of instructional skills, job performance, and coaching and mentoring competencies are often manifested/evident. Moderate descriptive level with a range of mean of 2.60-3.39 means measures of instructional skills, job performance, and coaching and mentoring competencies are sometimes manifested/evident. Low descriptive level with a range of mean 1.80 – 2.59, which means measures on instructional skills, job performance, and coaching and mentoring competencies are seldom manifested/evident, and very low descriptive level with a range of mean 1.00 – 1.79, which means measures on instructional skills, job performance, and coaching and mentoring competencies are almost never manifested/evident.

All these instruments were developed by drawing on the findings of several relevant studies and evaluations of the relevant literature. Before they were administered, the drafts of these instruments were evaluated by a panel of experts for both their face validity and their content validity. The validation produced an overall mean score of 4.6, which is interpreted as excellent.

2.3 Design and Procedure

The researchers used the descriptive-correlational research design for this study. According to Ragab, AbdElazem, and Ali Hassan (2023), a descriptive correlational study is one in which the primary goal of the research is to describe the associations between variables rather than to discover a cause-and-effect link. In education, this design aids in finding and assessing problems with policies, procedures, and curriculum design. It also helps administrators devise and carry out workable solutions. This study used

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descriptive-correlational methods to explain the degree of instructional skills and job performance in terms of the elements that influence them and the level of coaching and mentoring competencies among the participating teachers. The relationship between the three variables of this research was examined to discover if coaching and mentoring competencies mediate the relationship between the instructional skills and their job performance.

The study also employed a mediation approach. Mediation analysis (path analysis) within the non-experimental approach is a test that assesses whether a mediation effect is significant. Accordingly, it examines how the independent and dependent variables relate to one another and how they relate to the mediation factor (Blair, 2018). Mediation analysis aims to clarify how exposure affects the result (Nguyen, Schmid, & Stuart, 2021). Practical intervention components can be identified by mediation analysis, making it a valuable statistical technique in prevention research. Including models with binary variables and an exposure-mediator interaction, any mediation model aims to assess natural direct and indirect effects (Rijnhart, Valente, Smyth & MacKinnon, 2021).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Instructional Skills

Table 1 shows the level of instructional skills of the junior high school teachers in Island Garden City of Samal, with an overall mean of 4.20 with a very high descriptive level. It indicates that instructional skills are always manifested. This result means that items relating to instructional skills are primarily favorable. It can also be gleaned from the table that the indicator explication got the highest mean scores of 4.29, a very high descriptive level, and the lowest indicator structure got a 4.10 mean score with a high described level. This implies that products connected to instructional skills are essentially beneficial. Teachers are, therefore, exceptionally skilled in presenting ideas, providing clear instructions, ensuring their pupils understand the material, and enhancing the results of their learning. A good learning environment and improved academic success depend on these abilities.

Table 1: Level of Instructional Skills

	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Structure	0.60	4.10	High
Explication	0.58	4.29	Very High
Stimulation	0.59	4.17	High
Validation	0.57	4.17	High
Instruction	0.61	4.24	Very High
Comprehension	0.60	4.22	Very High
Activation	0.57	4.17	High
Student Learning Outcomes	0.68	4.20	Very High
Overall	0.52	4.20	Very High

Besides, regarding the form of explication with very high result it means that the explaining is a form of scaffolding which alludes the students to have comprehension of what is being studied, and every student needs to receive an individual explanation by the teacher making use of the explicit language (Lukmawardani, 2022). This means that teachers should be in a position to deliver instruction if they are to discern an improvement in student's performance. Teachers need training in putting into practice empirically supported practices for them to offer effective and sound instruction across curricular areas (Didion, Toste, & Filderman, 2020).

3.2 Job Performance

Table 2 displays the level of job performance of Island Garden City junior high school teachers. The job performance was always precise since the mean score of 4.26 was very close to the high descriptive level, which revealing that job performance is always present. Interpersonal relation is the highest mean with the mean score mean of 4.34 or a very high level. Teaching skills, the lowest mean score amongst the above indicators had a mean score of 4.14 or high level. Emphasis on opening up teaching strategies and training a faculty that is committed to ongoing learning, can take this area to an even higher level.

Table 2: Level of Job Performance

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Teaching Skills	0.52	4.14	High
Management Skills	0.55	4.26	Very High
Discipline and Regularity	0.56	4.31	Very High
Interpersonal Relations	0.55	4.34	Very High
Overall	0.48	4.26	Very High

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This implies that job performance is measured by how well they accomplish a task or by their ability to skillfully combine appropriate behavior to achieve organizational goals and objectives. In other words, teachers' job performance is about how well they contribute to the school's organizational goals and objectives in whatever area they are assigned to (Onaolapo, Olaji, & Onaolapo, 2019). Specifically, the very high level of interpersonal relations, as observed in the data, means the capacity of a teacher to plan interactions with students and ascertain how they communicate with each other. A teacher can demonstrate himself in pedagogical activity comprehensively only if actively exercises interpersonal communication with colleagues, students, and management in interpersonal relations (Boiko, Mitichkina, Petrenko, & Chubova, 2024).

3.3 Coaching and Mentoring Competencies

Shown in Table 3 are the mean scores for the coaching and mentoring competencies of the junior high school in Island Garden City of Samal, with an overall mean of 4.12, described as high level. This shows that mentoring and coaching competencies are often manifested. The high level could be attributed to the respondents' high marks for most items. Managing the goals, with a mean of 4.21, and me generally, with a mean of 4.22, are the highest-scoring areas, highlighting that teachers excel in both setting and managing goals, as well as in self-awareness and personal effectiveness. On the other hand, community through concepts and models with a mean of 3.96 has the lowest mean score but still falls within the high category. These skills show great capacity for personal and professional development, goal formulation, and achievement. Smith and Brown (2024) claim that goal-setting techniques significantly improve teacher effectiveness and student outcomes, therefore underlining the important part well-defined goals play in the success of education.

The lower mean suggests that there could be chances for more concentrated training or resources to improve their capacity to build and sustain community using these frameworks, therefore indicating possible areas for further development in this aspect of their responsibility. This implies that teachers are generally successful in their duties by having a high awareness of the fundamental abilities needed for mentoring and coaching.

Table 3: Level of Coaching and Mentoring Competencies

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Committed to Own Learning	0.54	4.16	High
Managing the Relationship	0.51	4.07	High
Managing the Goals	0.51	4.21	Very High
Self-awareness	0.50	4.12	High
Behavioral Awareness	0.50	4.10	High
Community through Concepts and Models	0.51	3.96	High
Communicating through Language	0.50	4.09	High
Business Savvy	0.49	4.18	High
Big Picture	0.48	4.05	High
Me Generally	0.53	4.22	Very High
Overall	0.42	4.12	High

This implies that although teachers are doing generally well, especially in goal management and self-awareness, their relatively poor performance in promoting community using conceptual models must be addressed. Using targeted professional development and training in this field, teachers can increase their capacity to create and maintain a supportive learning environment, enhancing the general efficacy and student results. This holds that coaching and mentoring are change practices that have gained force within organizations and have become vital in supporting the development of managers, employees, leaders, and entrepreneurs (Bozer & Delegach, 2019).

Supporting data emphasizes the need for these abilities. In line with the high scores in managing objectives, Smith and Brown (2024) indicate that goal-setting strategies significantly increase teacher effectiveness and student outcomes. Furthermore, as noted by Lee and Kim (2024), the need for self-awareness in professional development fosters great personal effectiveness and self-awareness performance.

3.4 Significance on the Relationship between Instructional Skills and Job Performance

Presented in Table 4.1 is the significant relationship drawn between instructional skills and job performance. It gained an overall r value of 0.708 and a p -value less than 0.05, manifesting a substantial correlation between the mentioned variables. This further suggests rejecting the hypothesis, saying there is no relationship between instructional skills and job performance. This implies that the intentional improvement of these abilities could lead to notable increases in teaching efficacy, classroom management, discipline, interpersonal interactions, and general job performance. This follows better student achievements, a more positive school climate, and improved teacher job satisfaction and retention.

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The overall finding indicates a strong relationship between job performance and instructional skills. It shows a strong correlation between the independent and dependent variables, and it is consistent with Goker's (2021) study findings, which indicated that a teacher's level of concern for a particular aspect of teaching would play a significant role in improving instructional skills. Stated differently, teachers will focus more attention and make more substantial efforts to improve a particular instructional component if they are more concerned about it. The study also underlined the importance of teachers as critical players in the teaching and learning process and their duty to incorporate the curriculum into instructional activities. To what degree instructors can create and implement instructional techniques in their classrooms is a determining factor in effective teaching (Budnyk, 2019).

Table 4.1: Significance of the Relationship between Instructional Skills and Job Performance

Instructional Skills	Job Performance				
	Teaching Skills	Management Skills	Discipline and Regularity	Interpersonal Relations	Overall
Structure	.503** (.000)	.474** (.000)	.332** (.000)	.412** (.000)	.485** (.000)
Explication	.582** (.000)	.579** (.000)	.504** (.000)	.577** (.000)	.633** (.000)
Stimulation	.575** (.000)	.608** (.000)	.511** (.000)	.539** (.000)	.629** (.000)
Validation	.584** (.000)	.629** (.000)	.524** (.000)	.534** (.000)	.641** (.000)
Instruction	.533** (.000)	.584** (.000)	.517** (.000)	.565** (.000)	.621** (.000)
Comprehension	.556** (.000)	.624** (.000)	.544** (.000)	.514** (.000)	.632** (.000)
Activation	.558** (.000)	.583** (.000)	.506** (.000)	.489** (.000)	.603** (.000)
Student Learning Outcomes	.597** (.000)	.615** (.000)	.537** (.000)	.618** (.000)	.668** (.000)
Overall	.646** (.000)	.677** (.000)	.573** (.000)	.614** (.000)	.708** (.000)

3.5 Significance on the Relationship between Instructional Skills and Coaching and Mentoring Competencies

Table 4.2 presents the findings from a test examining the connections between coaching and mentoring competencies and instructional skills. The overall values indicate a favorable and significant association between coaching and mentoring competencies and instructional skills, as demonstrated by the results. The overall r-value of .710 with a p-value less than 0.05, which indicates a positive correlation between coaching and mentoring competencies and instructional skills, suggests that the null hypothesis is rejected. The two variables are, therefore, positively correlated.

Table 4.2: Significance of the Relationship between Instructional Skills and Coaching and Mentoring Competencies

Instructional Skills	Coaching and Mentoring Competencies
Structure	.553** (.000)
Explication	.635** (.000)
Stimulation	.627** (.000)
Validation	.643** (.000)
Instruction	.620** (.000)
Comprehension	.607** (.000)
Activation	.640** (.000)
Student Learning Outcomes	.612** (.000)
Overall	.710** (.000)

Strategic investment in professional development, including these competencies, assures constant improvement and success throughout the educational environment. It validates Tinaytina's (2021) study, which claimed that instructors, as mentees, oversee the creation of lesson plans and instruct pupils at all educational levels. Their responsibilities encompass assigning homework, grading examinations, and recording the advancement of students. Instructors must be capable of covering a wide range of topics

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and interacting with students through well-designed lesson plans. They should be skilled professionals with an extensive understanding of legal education procedures and best practices in instruction as mentees. Giving new instructors the chance to collaborate closely with mentors benefits the teacher and the pupils.

Instructional skills were also much more beneficial for teachers guiding their peers. Teachers who excelled in lesson planning, classroom management, and adaptive teaching were more adept at giving their peers helpful criticism and modeling successful techniques. The research also found that good coaching improved the coached teachers' students' academic performance and teaching abilities (Smith & Jone, 2024).

3.6 Significance on the Relationship between Coaching and Mentoring Competencies and Job Performance

A significant correlation with a r -value of 0.761 was found between job performance and their coaching and mentoring competencies, as shown in Table 4.3. This suggests that each variable's unique capabilities are highly relevant. This leads to the null hypothesis being rejected. Job performance of teachers and coaching and mentoring competencies have a strong and positive association, as indicated by the correlation coefficient of .761**. Greater levels of coaching and mentoring competencies are correlated with greater levels of job performance in this instance, as suggested by the positive value (.761). The p -value of less than .05 indicates that the link found is statistically significant. The link between coaching and mentoring competencies and job performance is essentially improbable to be the result of chance, as indicated by a p -value less than .05.

Table 4.3: Significance of Relationship between Coaching and Mentoring Competencies and Job Performance

Coaching and Mentoring Competencies	Job Performance				Overall
	Teaching Skills	Management Skills	Discipline and Regularity	Interpersonal Relations	
	.751** (.000)	.676** (.000)	.566** (.000)	.708** (.000)	.761** (.000)

This implies that many facets of teachers' performance need improvement using effective mentorship and coaching. Improvements in teaching skills, classroom management, discipline, and interpersonal relationships correspond with competencies in mentoring and coaching. Strong mentoring and coaching abilities of teachers also show better general job efficiency. This emphasizes the need to fund these skills so that instructors may fulfill their jobs with increasing effectiveness.

The table indicates that job performance and coaching and mentoring competencies have a positive and statistically significant association. It suggests that teams are more likely to be ready for job performance when they exhibit higher coaching and mentoring competencies. The findings of the studies by Al-Kiyumi & Hammad (2020) and Nilda, Rivera, & Martinez (2020), which show that mentoring and coaching competencies positively correlate with job performance, indicate that educational mentoring serves to both enhance the caliber of teaching teachers and promote the development of the teaching profession. It includes offering facilities that facilitate a seamless learning process, raising the caliber of teachers' knowledge and skills, and offering guidance and coaching regarding curriculum implementation, the choice and application of teaching methods, learning tools, procedures, and teaching evaluation techniques. However, according to Szekely, Whiley, Pontes, & McDowall (2024), more data is needed to substantiate the current links between job performance and mentoring roles. In addition, Piazza and Rizzari's (2020) study suggests that coaching chances ought to be planned and executed to enhance faculty instructing methods.

Mediation Analysis of the Three Variables

Mediation analysis requires four steps to consider the third variable as a mediator. The steps that fell into the Steps 1 through 4 categories are shown in Table 5—the substantial direct impact of job performance on instructional skills in Step 1. Step 2 shows that coaching and mentoring competencies, the mediator (M), are significantly impacted by instructional skills. The analysis findings, shown in Step 3, indicate that their coaching and mentoring competencies highly predict job performance. As a result of the correlation between routes a, b, and c, more mediation analysis using Medgraph is required to ascertain the importance of the mediation effect. Using the Sobel z test, full mediation is achieved if the analysis is completed without a statistically significant impact of the independent variable on the dependent variable.

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Table 5: Regression analysis showing the influence of instructional skills on job performance as mediated by coaching and mentoring competencies

Step	Path	B	S.E.	B
1	C	.654	.038	.708***
2	A	.575	.033	.710***
3	B	.593	.057	.520***
4	c'	.313	.046	.339***

Further evidence that some instructional skills are mediated by coaching and mentoring competencies while other components are directly influenced or indirectly affected by factors outside the paradigm comes from the fact that the regression coefficient is significantly reduced on the last step and remains significant, indicating that only partial mediation is achieved. Additionally, it was shown that the influence of instructional skills on job performance decreased after being mediated by coaching and mentoring competencies, as indicated in step 4 (designated as c'). Because the effect was found to be significant at $p < 0.05$, partial mediation took place in this case.

Table 6: Results of statistical analysis on presence (or absence) of mediating effect

Combination of Variables	Sobel z	p-value	Mediation
instructional skills coaching and mentoring competencies → job performance	8.956317	<0.05	Partial mediation

The image also displays the computed effect size for the mediation test observed between three variables. The degree to which instructional skills impact job performance is determined by the effect size, which is connected to the indirect path. The beta of instructional skills concerning teachers' job performance is responsible for the overall effect value of 0.654. The beta of instructional skills towards work performance with innovation capabilities included in the regression has a direct effect value of 0.313. The value of the original beta between job performance and instructional skills that now flows through coaching and mentoring competencies to job performance is known as the indirect impact value, or 0.575 ($a*b$, where "a" denotes the path IS à CAMC and "b" pertains to the path between CAMC à JP). The ratio index is calculated by dividing the indirect effect by the overall impact; in this example, 0.575 by 0.654 equals 0.880. Coaching and mentoring competencies account for approximately 88% of the overall impact of instructional skills on job performance.

According to the statistical study, job performance is mediated by coaching and mentoring competencies and instructional skills. This implies that these skills directly enhance job performance and are also indirectly used using other variables. Therefore, mentoring and coaching in staff development initiatives help maximize job performance. Apart from direct and indirect strategies for enhancing general performance as a central issue in school, strategic planning should be taught in training courses. This aligns with the Bridge (2024), which underlines the strategic need for mentoring and coaching in raising employee performance and development. Based on this study, companies who provide these top goals are more likely to assess their success using performance criteria and recognize and reward efforts at coaching. This corresponds with studies on the partial mediation impact of coaching on work performance and mentoring competencies.

Moreover, Athena Publishing (2024) addresses the effectiveness of instructional coaching in learning situations. Instructional coaching is an excellent instrument for advancing professional development, improving instructional quality, and attaining corporate goals. This confirms the emphasis of the research on instructional skills in work performance since it reveals that job performance and professional growth are substantially benefited by instructional coaching.

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Mediation Analysis

Sobel z	8.956317, $p < 0.05^*$
Percentage of the total effect that is mediated	52.121632%
Ratio of the indirect to direct effect	1.088626

Effect Size Measures

Unstandardized Coefficients

Total:	0.654
Direct:	0.313
Indirect:	0.575
Ratio Index:	0.879

Figure 2. Medgraph showing the Mediation Analysis

V. CONCLUSION AND RECCOMENDATION

In this section, conclusion depends on the findings pointed out in the study as outlined below. The respondent junior high school teachers in Island Garden City of Samal was highly skilled in instruction, highly performing in the job and highly effective in coaching and mentoring. Specific, targeted, and structured should be used to enhance the professional practice or career pathways: official mentoring programs; complex and evidence-based teaching and leadership interventions, and peer coaching and satisfaction should be purposefully deployed for ongoing practice advancement proactively. Another way is to support professional learning as well as to encourage teachers to take leadership positions to help sustain and further develop the already extraordinary standards and choice of competencies.

The study confirms a significant relationship between coaching and mentoring and job performance. In the same manner, there is an essential relationship between instructional skills and job performance. Also, the outcome demonstrates that coaching and mentoring competencies considerably partially mediated the association between job performance and instructional skills among the junior high school teachers in Island Garden City, Samal. Hence, it is advised that educators integrate job performance into all coaching and mentoring competencies. Those with a high learning maturity and limited mentoring experience should quickly adjust to the relationship, though many require a high initial clarity about expectations. Additionally, it is advised that educators support managers in improving their coaching and mentoring competencies by helping teachers become more productive. Teachers' technical and communication management skills also impact the quality of instruction they provide, inspiring students to learn and making them more resilient to setbacks.

Herzberg's Motivator-Hygiene Theory offers insight into the study's findings by distinguishing between factors that directly influence job satisfaction and those that prevent dissatisfaction. In this context, instructional skills coaching and mentoring competencies function as motivators and act as incentives, improving job performance using chances for personal development, appreciation, and success. This fits the noted notable influence of these abilities on employment performance. The partial mediation revealed in the study implies that although coaching and mentoring enhance job performance mainly through motivating reasons, they also interact with other variables that influence performance, including hygienic elements like working surroundings and administrative support. Therefore, maximizing job performance depends on a thorough strategy covering motivating and sanitary elements.

As a result, it is advised that educational institutions—especially department heads—pay more attention to raising general school performance by bettering instructional quality and prioritizing junior high school professional development programs. Although the Philippines has started several staff development programs, more focus on educating school leaders is needed. Improving teachers' performance depends on prioritizing leadership's functionality and quality. First, institutions should offer more hands-on training courses and seminars and create initiatives that allow mentees to interact more successfully with their mentors. Future studies should also investigate other elements that might moderate the interaction between several elements to better fit mentee training to changing demands.

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